

Effects of Hands-on Activity-Based and Demonstration Methods on Senior Secondary Students' Achievement in Physical Chemistry

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effects of hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods on senior secondary students' achievement in Physical Chemistry. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent quasi-experimental design. A sample of 172 students from six purposively selected secondary schools out of a population of 8,381 Senior Secondary II students from zone C of Benue State, Nigeria. The experimental groups were taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods while the control group were taught using discussion method. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. A validated 30-item Physical Chemistry Achievement Test (PCAT) was the instrument used to collect data. Reliability coefficient of 0.96 was established using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula. Mean and Standard Deviation scores were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that students taught using hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods had significantly higher mean achievement scores respectively than those taught using discussion method ($F=231.254$, $P(0.0001<0.05)$), ($F=182.125$, $P(0.0001<0.05)$). Students in hands-on activity-based and demonstration groups did not differ significantly in achievement ($F=23.060$, $P(0.166>0.05)$). It was recommended among others that chemistry teachers should be encouraged to adopt hands-on activity-based and demonstration teaching methods in teaching physical chemistry.

Key words: Hands-on activity-based, demonstration, achievement, physical chemistry.

INTRODUCTION

The development of any nation depends largely on the level of scientific and technological literacy possessed by its citizenry. The study of chemistry as one of the science subjects is of great importance, that a lot of emphasis has been laid on its teaching and learning with the major aim to equip the students to live effectively in this modern age (FRN, 2004). This can be achieved by the inculcation in the learners the necessary scientific skills and attitudes. The inculcation of scientific skills and attitudes in students can only be achieved through the proper teaching of chemistry. Chemistry when proper taught will help the students in the development of modern technology through the application of its knowledge in modern invention.

Chemistry is an experimental science that systematically studies the composition, properties and activities of substances and various elementary forms of matter. Its study involves exploration of relationship between theory and experiment. Physical Chemistry which is the main focus of this study is the study of macroscopic, atomic, subatomic, and particulate phenomena in chemical systems and has been found very useful in different fields of science and technology. It is utilized in electrochemical industries. Chemistry is a very important subject as its knowledge is required for the successful study in many important professions

Therefore, chemistry teachers should adopt appropriate methods that would enable the students to understand whatever concepts, topics or principle that are being taught. Chemistry teachers over time have used a number of teaching methods. Such methods are lecture, expository and discussion methods which are predominantly teacher centered. Studies have shown that these methods have not yielded expected results (Aliu, 2008). Adegoke (2013) also investigated the causes of students' under-achievement in Senior School Certificate

Examination (WAEC & NECO) physical Chemistry concepts and the most recurring factor in all the reports are the inefficient teaching methods employed by secondary school Chemistry teachers as mentioned earlier among such methods are lecture and discussion teaching methods.

Similarly, Adedayo (2015) noted that discussion method is popular in teaching/learning of Senior School Certificate Examination Physical Chemistry concept in Nigeria despite its limitations. The scholar further added that discussion method is teacher-centered as it does not involve the learners enough participation and the discussion may degenerate into mere talk and may be monopolized by few individuals. This may consequently lead to a conclusion far from the truth even though such may be accepted by the group as a whole. This has been alluded to have led to the failure of students in Chemistry in external examinations such as Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO).

Chemistry teaching can only be result oriented when students are willing and the teachers are favorably disposed to using appropriate methods and resources in teaching the students with the quest for scientific knowledge the world over, much demand is placed, and emphasis is laid on the teacher, the learner, the curriculum and the environment in the whole process of teaching and learning of science. Based on the relevance of Chemistry, it would be pertinent that Chemistry teachers should acquire appropriate methods that could equip them in understanding principles and concepts for effective learning outcomes specifically in physical chemistry. The appropriate method is that which is learner-centred or sometime called active learning such as cooperative learning, inquiry, hands-on activity-based, demonstration and so on. This study focused on use of hands-on activity-based and demonstration learning.

Abudullai (2013) describes hands-on activity-based as a method of teaching whereby students are engaged actively in class activities with the use of their hands and intellect under the guidance of the teacher. The author adds that teaching and learning processes which involves hands-on activity-based is believed to help students in understanding theories and principles which may be difficult or abstract in nature. Tile (2013) also described hands-on activity-based as a situation where a learner uses his/her hands in carrying out activities that could enhance his/her experiences, therefore enhancing his/her achievement in such concepts and to a larger extent the subject. By implication, concrete activities experiences are activities which involve doing and using apparatus or objects. These include weighting, measuring, demonstrating, carrying out tests/experiments and any other concrete activities that could enhance students' achievement in such concepts such as physical chemistry taught conventionally in senior secondary schools.

Demonstration method is referred to as teaching through displaying something, which is visible, audio visual explanation of idea, process or product. It involves showing, doing and telling the students the point of emphasis (Abe, 2007). Anyagh (2008) revealed that no matter how suitable the educational objectives and content might be, the curriculum process will remain defective if viable instructional methods are not adopted in the task of teaching. Ajayi (2017) opined that if effective modality is not put in place to incorporate innovative methods that promote active learning and considering the importance of chemistry in all round development, the nation's quest for science and technology advancement will become a mirage. Hence the needs to find innovative methods that promote active learning. Therefore, this study examined the effects of hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods on students' achievement in Physical Chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using demonstration method and those taught using discussion method?
3. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using demonstration method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using demonstration method and those taught using discussion method.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using demonstration method.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND PROCEDURE

The study used pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design. The study area was zone C of Benue State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 8,381 SSII students in the 132 granted aided secondary schools. 172 students were purposively sampled from 6 of the schools that had some basic facilities and equipment in their laboratories. During lessons, the teachers used as research assistant taught the experimental group 1 physical Chemistry

topics using hands-on activity-based lesson notes and the experimental group 2 was taught using demonstration method while the control group was taught the same physical Chemistry topics using the discussion lesson notes. An instrument known as Physical Chemistry Achievement Test (PCAT) developed by the researchers and validated by two experts of science education and one other expert of measurement and evaluation all from Benue State University, Makurdi was used to collect the data. The PCAT, a 30 item multiple choice instruments yielded reliability coefficients of 0.96 using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) formula. Mean and Standard Deviation scores were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using discussion method?

The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on Activity-based Method and Discussion Method.

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	δ	$\bar{x}$	δ	
Hands-on Activity-based	57	12.72	1.11	27.12	1.93	14.40
Discussion	59	12.70	1.15	15.35	1.77	2.65
Mean difference		0.02		11.77		11.75

Table 1 reveals that, the overall mean difference between two groups was 11.75 in favour of hands-on activity-based. This implies that students taught using hands-on activity-based method achieved higher than their discussion group counterparts.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using demonstration method and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question two is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Demonstration Method and Discussion Method.

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	δ	$\bar{x}$	δ	
Demonstration	56	12.71	1.16	26.34	1.86	13.63
Discussion	59	12.70	1.15	15.35	1.77	2.65
Mean difference		0.01		10.99		10.98

Table 2 reveals that, the overall mean difference between two groups was 10.98 in favour of demonstration method. This implies that students taught using demonstration method achieved higher than their discussion group counterparts.

Research Question Three

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using demonstration method? The answer to research question three is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on Activity-based Method and Demonstration Method.

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		$\bar{x}$	δ	$\bar{x}$	δ	
Hands-on Activity-based	57	12.72	1.11	27.12	1.93	14.40
Demonstration	56	12.71	1.16	26.34	1.86	13.63
Mean difference		0.01		0.78		0.77

Table 3 reveals that, the overall mean difference between two groups was 0.77 in favour of hands-on activity-based. This implies that students taught using hands-on activity-based achieved slightly higher than their demonstration group counterparts.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and discussion method. The answer to hypothesis one is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on Activity-based and Discussion Method.

Source	Type III sum of square	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1700.332a	2	405.083	135.821	.000
Intercept	1792.021	1	1792.021	472.081	.000
Pre-test	297.305	1	297.305	76.084	.000
Method	1394.128	1	1394.128	231.254	.000
Error	699.300	169	6.010		
Total	119306.010	172			
Corrected Total	2101.690	171			

a. R squared = .214 (Adjusted R Squared= .211)

Table 4 reveals that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores between the students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based and those taught discussion method in favour of hands-on activity-based ($F(1,171) = 231.254, p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore not accepted. This means that hands-on activity-based enhanced students' achievement in physical chemistry

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using demonstration method and those taught using discussion method. The answer to hypothesis two is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Demonstration Method and Discussion Method.

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1340.010a	2	320.062	131.360	.000
Intercept	1700.001	1	1700.001	532.071	.000
Pre-test	244.125	1	244.125	67.074	.000
Method	1134.087	1	1134.087	182.125	.000
Error	701.361	169	3.100		
Total	129326.900	172			
Corrected Total	1901.393	171			

a. R squared = .350 (Adjusted R Squared= .345)

Table 5 reveals that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores between the students taught physical chemistry using demonstration method and those taught discussion method in favour of demonstration method ($F(1, 171) = 182.125, p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore not accepted. This means that demonstration method enhanced students' achievement in physical chemistry

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based method and those taught using demonstration method. The answer to hypothesis three is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: ANCOVA Tests for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Physical Chemistry using Hands-on Activity-based Method and Demonstration Method

Source	Type III sum of square	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected model	1486.301a	2	505.091	195.985	.000
Intercept	1890.001	1	1890.001	772.567	.000
Pre-test	217.985	1	217.985	71.184	.000
Method	1031.828	1	1031.828	23.060	.166
Error	512.201	169	5.121		
Total	109006.000	172			
Corrected Total	2400.090	171			

a. R squared = .254 (Adjusted R Squared= .249)

Table 6 reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between the students taught physical chemistry using hands-on activity-based and those taught demonstration method ($F(1,171)=23.060, p>0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore accepted.

DISCUSSION

The study examined the effects of hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods on achievement of senior secondary two students in physical chemistry. The independent variables were the teaching methods (hands-on activity-based and demonstration). The findings of this study revealed that students taught Physical Chemistry using hands-on activity-based achieved higher than their counterparts taught using discussion method. This finding agrees with Wasiu (2013) who found that students achieved higher

when exposed to hands-on activity-based than their counterparts that were exposed to traditional method in Biology. The high achievement was recorded when hands-on activity-based was used in instructional delivery probably because the method allow students to actively participate in carrying out activities by themselves while the teacher assumes the role of a facilitator, mediator and assessor of learning. This supports earlier report by Felder (2012) who asserted that children learn best by doing not just by sitting and listening. The finding also indicated that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Physical Chemistry using demonstration and those taught using discussion method in favour of demonstration method.

The finding is in conformity with Omowumi (2015) who found that students achieved higher when exposed to demonstration method than their counterparts that were exposed to traditional method in physic. However, the likely reason for the agreement of these finding could be that demonstration method enhanced students' achievement because it involve the audio-visual explanation of ideas or concept in comparison with the one they only hear. The finding also revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Physical Chemistry using hands-on activity-based and those taught using demonstration method. This implies that hands-on activity-based and demonstration method has great effects on students' achievement in Physical Chemistry more so that it helps to practicalize those concepts in physical Chemistry which are mostly abstract in nature in order to reduce them to concreteness or to reduce their degree of abstraction. In this way, students are motivated and materials are internalized more easily.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods could enhance student achievement in physical chemistry. If hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods proposed by this study are adopted in physical chemistry teaching and learning it will likely boost the achievement of students. Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since students in the hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods groups were found to achieve higher, the methods should be encouraged to be used by chemistry teachers in teaching physical chemistry.
2. Hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods require that, there should be standard laboratory and sufficient instructional materials. Therefore, schools should provide good laboratory, sufficient instructional materials for students and teachers to carryout necessary activities in Physical chemistry through hands-on activity-based and demonstration methods respectively.

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